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Discrete Movement as a Key to Quantum Measurements Understanding

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Abstract. Any quantum measurement (except for special cases of pure state) is accompanied by an instantaneous transition of a quantum entity from one state to another. This is the so-called quantum leap. The accompanying phenomena are nonlocality and wave–particle duality. Using the model of discrete motion, we can not only clearly explain these “mysterious” processes, but also depict them in simple drawings.

Key words: Quantum measurement; Quantum leap; Nonlocality; Wave–particle duality; Discrete motion model; Wave packet; Mach-Zehnder interferometer.

Introduction

If quantum theory does not cause disturbances at first, then it cannot be that it is correctly understood, said Niels Bohr [1]. But then time passed, all disturbances subsided, and it is time to understand: what exactly in quantum mechanics causes the strongest rejection?

In the microcosm there are only three phenomena that have no analogues in classical physics. This is wave–particle duality, nonlocality, and quantum leaps.

Wave–particle duality means that an indivisible electron (or any other quantum particle) can pass through two (or more) holes simultaneously. Nonlocality means that there is an instantaneous action at a distance (read "Quantum Nonlocality" *Measurements World*, 2013, No7). A quantum leap (it is described by collapse of a wave function) is an instantaneous transition of a quantum entity (or system of quantum entities) from one state to another.

We can easily tell about these three phenomena, but it is hard to believe that they exist in reality. For example, Erwin Schrödinger did not believe in quantum leaps and even wrote an article about this “Are there quantum jumps?” [2]. He called quantum mechanics to be magic and Louis de Broglie agreed with him [3]. Almost all physicists who conducted experiments to detect nonlocality did not believe in such a phenomenon, since they were followers of Albert Einstein and John Bell in this matter. By their experiments, they wanted to prove that there is no nonlocality in nature, but they proved the opposite.

In comparison with a quantum leap or a nonlocal bond, the passage of an electron through two holes looks like an innocent prank. But it is hard to imagine. It seems intuitively obvious that an indivisible electron cannot be in different spots at the same time. What is the reason for this contradiction? Clearly, it is not about the electron (no matter how intricately it moves), but about our minds. Contradiction can arise only in our minds. Simply put, there is an idea in our minds that we implicitly use when trying to understand the motion of an electron. It is the usage of this idea that leads to the contradiction.

What is this idea? This is the notion of a continuous trajectory. After all, a trajectory is an infinitely thin line. It is a geometric abstraction, which is the extrapolation of experimental data. In the microcosm, this extrapolation fails. It is no accident that many courses of quantum mechanics begin with the following, “In quantum mechanics, there is no concept of particle trajectory” [4]. If an electron does not move along a continuous trajectory, then how does it move? An alternative to continuous motion is a discontinuous motion, which we will henceforth call discrete. Let us see what it is.

Discrete motion

Let us consider an electron (for definiteness we will speak of an electron, but it can be any quantum particle: photon, neutron, proton, atom, and etc.), whose state is described in the general case by a complex wave function $\Psi(x, y, z)$. Let this function be nonzero only in the region of the space G (see Fig. 1a).

Fig. 1. a) A region of space, at all points of which the electron “is present”. b) This region is similar to a cloud of virtual electrons. Each of them is indicated by a small circle with an arrow indicating a direction of movement.

According to the orthodox Copenhagen interpretation, this means that an electron is present

immediately at all points of this region with a probability proportional to the Ψ -function module squared.

If a point electron moved along a continuous trajectory, it could not fill the entire region G , which can be large. Therefore, we can assume that within the region G , the electron moves **discretely**, namely: at a time t , it is at some point in the region, then it disappears from this point and in an infinitely small period dt appears at another, arbitrary point, also inside this region. Thus, for any arbitrarily small but finite time interval (say, for a period $\Delta t < 10^{-23}$ seconds, it is the time for which the light travels the distance equal to a nucleus of the atom), the electron has time to disappear and appear at all points of the region G . Moreover, at each point, it succeeds in appearing and disappearing an infinite number of times, having a different momentum (velocity) at the same time. Therefore, at each arbitrarily small, but finite time interval, the electron is at once at all points of a certain region of the phase space – the space (x, y, z, p_x, p_y, p_z) . The frequency of appearance of an electron at a given point of the region is proportional to $|\Psi|^2$. We will correct our picture taking into account the fact that at each point the electron has different velocities and that the probability of its being at different points of the region is different (see Fig. 1b). The region of space where the Ψ -function is non-zero is sometimes called a wave packet.

Now let us see what we can expect from a particle that moves not continuously, but discretely.

Spreading and splitting a wave packet

Fig. 2. An electron is located at all points of some region at the same time (a). Then this area moves in space changing its size and shape (b). It is a so-called spreading of a wave packet.

If an electron performs a discrete motion in a certain region and at the same time it has different values of velocity (different magnitude and direction) at different points, then we can expect that this region (wave packet) will gradually spread in space. In addition, the region itself can move as a whole one. As a result, we have a picture of movement, schematically depicted in Fig. 2.

Now suppose that the region where the electron moves discretely is placed in a sealed box with impermeable walls. In this case, the area will increase in size until it fills the entire box. What happens if we divide the box in half by a partition, which, like its walls, does not interact with the electron? The partition will not

interfere with the electron to move inside the entire box, since it moves not along a continuous trajectory, but discretely: it disappears from one point and appears in the other one.

So, we have two boxes isolated from each other, inside of which only one electron moves discretely (Fig. 3a). If we start to move them away from each other, then the electron will continue to move discretely, being still in both boxes (Fig. 3b). A distance between the boxes can be made arbitrarily large – the electron will be simultaneously in two boxes (Fig. 3c). This is the splitting of the wave packet.

Fig. 3. Splitting a wave packet

An example of such discrete motion in two isolated regions is the behavior of an electron in an atom (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of a distribution of the probability density of an electron’s location in an atom for the 2p state [5]. The figure shows a cut in the plane XY. The distribution of a probability density is symmetrical about the Y axis, so the exact same distribution graph will also be in the plane YZ. The greatest probability of the location of the electron is at the center of each “petal”, and it is zero in the plane XZ. From the viewpoint of classical (continuous) motion, it is impossible to explain how an electron can be in both petals without intersecting the plane XZ.

Thus, if a region where an electron makes discrete motion (a wave function is non-zero) can split into two halves then after splitting into two parts it will move in different directions. The electron making discrete motion will also move simultaneously in different directions. For example, it can go through two holes at the same time. If later the regions are connected on the detector, then their interference will take place. The motion of any other quantum particle (for example, a photon) will be similarly.

Quantum measurement is a quantum leap

Let a region with a discretely moving electron runs into an obstacle and dividing into two wave packets it bypass the obstacle from different sides. What happens if we after measuring the location of an electron “catch” it in one of two wave packets?

As soon as this happens the probability of finding an electron in any other spot will be zero. Therefore, the wave packet where we detect the exact location of the electron instantly will shrink to a point (decrease to a very small area). The second packet will disappear without trace (see Fig. 5). This is an example of the famous quantum leap. Mathematically, it is described by the collapse of a wave function.

Fig. 5. Quantum leap

The wave packet where the electron moves discretely hits the obstacle and after dividing into two packets it bypasses the obstacle from both sides. In a vicinity of point A, the electron interacts with a classical object (measurement), as a result of which it gets the exact location. After that, the probability of detecting an electron, for example in a vicinity of point B, becomes zero, and the wave packet in the vicinity of point A contracts to point-like volume. Mathematically, this process is described by the collapse of a wave function.

Prior to measuring the location of an electron, its motion was completely described by a Ψ -function, which continuously varied in time. The measurement process is NOT described by a Ψ -function. After the measurement has occurred, the old Ψ function will be struck out, and a new one will be written based on the measurement results. It can be noted that the measurement process in quantum mechanics is fundamentally different from the measurement in classical physics. When we want to measure the exact location of an electron we use a device that *forces* the electron to take the exact location. Before measuring, the electron *did not have* a specific location.

Nonlocality and the superposition principle

If we do not “interfere” with the movement of the electron, then the wave packet in which it is located can split into countless parts. These parts can move in different directions, but their behavior will be described by a common wave function. Simply put, a single electron can represent a rather complex motion (see Fig. 6). In this case, the motion of all wave packets will be related to each other by nonlocal bonds. As soon as we detect an electron in one of them the others ones will disappear without any trace.

Fig. 6. A wave packet containing one electron runs into an obstacle and, dividing into two parts, bypasses the obstacle from two sides. The formed wave packets partially pass through the holes and are partially reflected from them. As a result, one electron can form a very complex motion, consisting of a multitude of wave packets. Their motion is completely determined by the Schrodinger wave equation and therefore it is absolutely deterministic in time. The random nature of quantum processes manifests itself only at the instant of a quantum leap. The quantum leap is not described by any equation of motion.

The basic principle of quantum mechanics is the superposition principle. If an electron can be on Earth (denote this state Ψ_E) and on the Moon (state Ψ_M), then it can also be in the state: $\Psi_E + \Psi_M$. This means that an indivisible electron can be physically present both on Earth and on the Moon at the same time. The superposition principle implies nonlocality. If we measure a location of an electron in a wave packet on Earth, we can have two options. We “catch” an electron and the second wave packet disappears without a trace. We “do not catch” the electron and then the probability of finding it in the second wave packet immediately increases to 100 percent. That is, for any measurement outcome, the state of the second wave packet changes discontinuously.

The discrete motion model allows visualizing such a strange behavior of an electron. In addition, it allows us

to understand how to prepare a similar state. To do this, we need to take an electron, wait until its wave packet spreads, then divide it into two parts and deliver one part to the Moon. It is clear that the two parts of the wave packet belonging to one electron are *physically* connected. This connection *does not depend on distance*. It is also obvious that a quantum leap, accompanied by the destruction of one wave packet, is *irreversible* in time. That is, the process of collapse of a quantum state cannot be reversed.

Mach-Zehnder interferometer

Almost everyone who first find out about the “paradoxes” of wave–particle duality begins to doubt the correctness of the interpretation of such experiments. Is the electron (photon) moving really at once along two paths? Maybe the interference pattern is a consequence of some interactions between *different* particles, but each particle, being an indivisible quantum entity, moves strictly along one path?

Fig. 7. The Mach-Zehnder interferometer

Consider an experiment in which interference effects are manifested with the participation of just *one* particle. Photons are emitted from the laser one by one (Fig. 7). After a photon reaches the first beam splitter (semitransparent mirror), it can move either along the first path or along the second one or along both paths simultaneously. Moving along the first path it is reflected from the mirror 1 and moving along the second path it is reflected from the mirror 2. Then both paths intersect again on the beam splitter 2 after which the photon can be detected either by the detector 1 or by the detector 2, but never both simultaneously. That is, each photon is always detected by only one detector. The first way is covered by a thin glass plate 1. Its purpose is to increase the optical path length of the photon, as a result of which the photon, moving along the first path, comes to the second beam splitter with some phase lag. By varying the thickness of the glass plate any arbitrary phase shift can be achieved. Instead of a glass plate, any device capable of increasing (changing) the optical path length

can be used. A similar device can be used in the second way.

Let us try to predict the results of this experiment based on common sense. Since a photon is always detected by only one detector then, consequently, it moves along one path. Therefore, after passing the beam splitter a photon with a probability of say 50% passes through it and moves along the second path and with a probability of 50% it is reflected from it and moves along the first path. The photon moves similarly to reach the second beam splitter. Thus, each photon flying out of the laser will move along one of all possible paths and it will be detected by one of the two detectors with 50% probability.

From this viewpoint, an increase in the optical path length of one of the interferometer’s arms will not lead to any noticeable effects. A photon will simply reach the detector with some phase delay.

What do we observe in the experiment? By varying the optical length of the first path we can achieve that fewer and fewer photons will fall on the first detector. With a certain increase in the optical length of the first path, *no photon* will fall into the first detector. They will all be detected only by the second one (Fig. 8). Continuing the further change in the optical path length we can achieve the opposite result: all the photons will be detected only by the first detector.

Fig. 8. By selecting a glass plate of the desired thickness, we can achieve that all photons without exception will only fall into the 2nd detector and vice versa.

Suppose for greater clarity that near the first path there is an experimenter and in his hands he holds a “key”, that is a device capable of smoothly changing the optical path length. By changing a position of this key the experimenter can at his discretion make sure that all the photons are falling only on the first detector or, conversely, only on the second one. The experimenter has the right to conclude that *all* the photons are moving along the first path because he *controls the motion of all photons* with his key.

The second experimenter with a similar key can stand in the second path. Manipulating his key, he will

also conclude that all the photons are moving along the second path.

So, this experiment makes sure that *each* photon moves along two different paths simultaneously. It turns out that a photon, splitting at the beam splitter, moves in the form of two wave packets immediately along two different paths. Their interference is observed on the detector. Increasing the optical length of one of the paths, we change a phase of a wave packet moving along it and thereby influence the result of the interference.

However, if we try to catch two wave packets at once then we will not succeed. As soon as a photon is detected in one of them the second wave packet will disappear.

This experiment is considered the most difficult to understand. For example, the famous modern specialist in quantum computing David Deutsch [7] after analyzing it comes to the conclusion that the “photon double” from the parallel world moves along the second path! Based on this experiment Deutsch tries to prove that there are many different universes.

If we use the model of discrete motion, then it is not difficult to give an interpretation to the experiment. First, the photon is split at the first beam splitter into two wave packets. Then each of these packets is split into two packets at the 2nd beam splitter. As a result, four wave packets are formed, within which one photon moves discretely. In this case, two packets, interfering with each other, are moving to the first detector, and the other two packets are moving to the second one. By varying the optical length of only one path it is possible to achieve that the wave packets will arrive at the first detector in antiphase, and on the second one, respectively, in phase. That is, creating an additional phase shift of only one wave packet we *control* the motion of a photon that moves discretely in 4 wave packets at once.

Conclusion

A quantum entity, as a rule, does not have any specific characteristics of motion: exact location, pulse, and projection of the spin. This is due to the fact that the quantum entity can be in a superposition of different states, while possessing an entire set of all possible velocities and coordinates. If an experimenter wants to measure, say, the coordinate (momentum, spin projection), he uses a device that *forces* the quantum entity to assume a specific location (momentum, spin projection). Therefore, almost any process of quantum measurement is accompanied by a so-called quantum leap – the instantaneous transition of a quantum entity from one state to another. This process is described by collapse of the wave function and it is irreversible in time. The quantum leap is directly related to the basic principle of quantum mechanics – the superposition principle.

The state of a quantum entity and its evolution are completely described by the wave function. The discrete motion model, allowing visualizing the Ψ -function, gives an opportunity to visualize how any process proceeds in the microcosm. Using the discrete motion model, we can show in simple pictures why the process of quantum

measurement leads to a quantum leap, and why this process is irreversible in time.

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